

ASSESSMENT OF THE RISK OF DEVELOPING ALOPECIA IN PATIENTS AFTER CORONAVIRAL INFECTION AND EFFECTIVE TREATMENT METHODS

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Abstract: Approximately every fourth or fifth person who has had a coronavirus infection begins to notice problems with hair, more precisely, with their loss. Unlike other consequences in the form of weakness, shortness of breath, this problem does not interfere with doing everyday things, but still brings discomfort and anxiety, especially if after the covid the hair climbs in clumps.

Key words: hair loss, telogen, anagen, catagen, nutrition, trichoscopy, baldness, hair follicle, pull-test, androgenic alopecia.

ОЦЕНКА РИСКА РАЗВИТИЯ АЛОПЕЦИИ У БОЛЬНЫХ, ПЕРЕНЕСШИХ КОРОНАВИРУСНУЮ ИНФЕКЦИЮ, И ЭФФЕКТИВНЫЕ МЕТОДЫ ЛЕЧЕНИЯ

Аннотация: примерно каждый четвертый-пятый человек, переболевший коронавирусной инфекцией, начинает замечать проблемы с волосами, точнее с их выпадением. В отличие от других последствий в виде слабости, одышки, эта проблема не мешает заниматься повседневными делами, но все равно приносит дискомфорт и беспокойство, особенно если после ковида волосы лезут клочьями.

Ключевые слова: выпадение волос, телоген, анаген, катаген, питание, трихоскопия, облысение, волосяной фолликул, пул-тест, андрогенная алопеция.

INTRODUCTION

Most patients after suffering from an infectious disease COVID - 19 experience a problem with hair. Some lose up to 90% of their hairline. The cause and influence of the virus itself, which damages the vascular endothelium, disrupts the nutrition of the hair follicle. Antiviral, antibacterial drugs, metabolites that are excreted through the skin accumulate in the hair.

The most common form of postcovid alopecia is diffuse. This option can be called favorable, since over time and in the absence of exposure to external toxic agents, the hairline is restored.

The second most common type of postcovid alopecia is alopecia areata. This option requires treatment by a specialist, sometimes for quite a long time, since it is already associated with damage to the immune system.

The third option is ischemic hair loss. It occurs in people who have suffered severe oxygen deficiency who were on oxygen support or mechanical ventilation. Some people may experience complete baldness - anogenic hair loss

MATERIALS AND METHODS

The database with the consequences after the coronavirus is constantly being updated, and the list has expanded with a relatively new problem – hair loss. According to the results of research by scientists from China, about 22-24% of patients who were treated for this disease began to complain about hair loss. Another one has been added to the already known post-cortical signs, such as a residual cough, a slight fever, weakness, a violation of the sense of smell, depression. According to research, it was revealed that hair problems began to occur about 2 months after the disease. Most often, the symptom is manifested in women, and there is a correlation between the severity of the disease, the intensity, duration of therapy and the activity of hair loss. Their loss is

noted even in those who have suffered the virus asymptotically. Alopecia after infection Experts note that people who have had coronavirus have a uniform loss of hair over the entire area of the head. There are no clear areas of baldness, characterized only by a significant decrease in the amount of hair, a violation of the structure of the hair shaft. Some patients note that the hair is literally falling from the head, others note that there is a little more hair loss than before the disease. With a more detailed study of the problem, experts noted that the life cycle of the hair is lost in those who have been ill. This type of baldness is called telogen. That is, the hair freezes in the resting phase, in other words, they simply stop growing and do not move into the next phase of the cycle. The activity of the follicles is greatly reduced or completely absent. Many people believe that the hair on the head grows constantly, but in fact this is not quite true, they have 3 phases of development:

Anagen is a growth period lasting 2-6 years.

Catagen is a transitional phase when atrophy of the hair papilla occurs, which provides nutrition to the bulb, while the hair itself ceases to grow. The duration of the phase is 1-3 weeks.

Telogen is a period of rest in which the hair root no longer receives blood supply and falls out during mechanical action, for example, combing.

After the loss, the blood supply in the area of the fallen hair is activated and the formation of a new one begins.

Every day a person loses about a hundred hairs, which is about 0.1% of the total volume. In a normal state, approximately 85% of the hair should be in the anagen phase, about 2% in the catagen stage and 10-15% in telogen. With telogen alopecia, most of the follicles enter the telogen phase compared to the norm, the catagen period is shortened, and the hair falls out after COVID-19, which leads to a noticeable decrease in volume. The role of a new infection in the development of androgenic alopecia, which is associated with the action of androgens on hair follicles, is discussed. There are a number of studies that demonstrate a link between hormones that are involved in the pathogenesis of covid and the possible development of androgenic alopecia. In particular, we are talking about androgen-regulated protease, which is a coreceptor necessary for infection with the virus.

Why does hair fall out so much after coronavirus There is not enough information about the mechanism of hair loss and violation of their structure due to infection. According to the observations of scientists, the virus specifically has no effect on hair follicles. Regarding hair problems, there are other assumptions, what is the reason for the deterioration of their condition: tissue nutrition, microcirculation of the scalp skin is disrupted, vascular coagulation occurs due to high temperature; intoxication of the body occurs against the background of the infectious process; interferon is actively produced, which is necessary to fight infection; there is a psychoemotional stress due to a confirmed diagnosis, an anxious state due to quarantine; the composition of the blood changes – the number of red blood cells decreases, the level of hemoglobin decreases, which leads to anemia; taking a large number of medications – antibiotics, anticoagulants, antihistamines, antiviral, nonsteroidal anti-inflammatory drugs and others necessary for effective treatment of the disease. This negatively affects the condition of the hair papilla, the division of the cells of the bulb. Such a voluminous list of negative factors that affect a weakened body from infection cannot but affect the condition of hair, skin and nails (some patients have such complaints). We must also not forget that during the period of any disease, appetite worsens, a person consumes less important nutrients, which leads to a deficiency of vitamins and trace elements. Therefore, there is nothing strange in the fact that the hair falls out a lot from covid.

Features of post-ovoid hair loss The activity of hair loss after the disease can be so high that it really scares patients. Causes additional stress, worsens the psychoemotional state, which so suffers from the infection. Upon examination, a sharply positive hair tension test (pull-test) is detected, and according to instrumental research methods, the percentage of hair loss is 25-30%, which significantly deviates from the norm of 10-15%. This fact indicates a high degree of involvement of follicles in the infectious process. Also, patients have a slowdown and insufficient growth of hair, which should replace the fallen out, which, as a rule, is not typical for telogen baldness, due to stress, vitamin deficiency, etc.

However, do not be upset, according to experts, this unpleasant consequence of the disease is a temporary and reversible phenomenon. As the body recovers, hair growth normalizes, and it takes about six months. But the return of volume, of course, requires a longer time. Fear can only be caused by situations when the hair follicle does not enter a new cycle, that is, a latent period begins in which the hair does not grow. In this case, the reasons are not entirely clear, the development of scar and nest alopecia may indicate immune disorders in the area of hair follicles. What to do if hair falls out after coronavirus. It will not be possible to cope with hair loss, recognized by the transferred coronavirus, on your own. It is possible to stop alopecia and then restore growth zones only by eliminating the key factors that caused this disease. This complex problem can be solved only with the help of a professional trichologist or dermatologist, who, only after a thorough diagnosis and diagnosis, will develop an effective treatment regimen.

RESULTS

First of all, do not panic and consult a trichologist so that he can diagnose and treat the necessary treatment. The specialist will prescribe a number of tests and studies based on the examination, anamnesis collection: trichoscopy; tests to determine the level of hormones, vitamins, trace elements and others; general and biochemical blood tests; a trichogram. Taking into account the data obtained, the trichologist develops treatment tactics for baldness after coronavirus. As a rule, it is complex and includes drug therapy, lifestyle correction, nutrition, the use of cosmeceuticals, etc.

Nutrition correction and intake of vitamin complexes

Hair growth requires magnesium, selenium, zinc, vitamins D and group B. The latter have a general strengthening effect, support the functioning of the nervous system, which allows you to cope with the effects of stress. Multivitamin preparations are prescribed in a course designed for 3-4 months.

DISCUSSION

At the same time, you need to make adjustments to your diet. To get enough iron, zinc and biotin, you need: seafood, leafy greens; eggs; whole grain cereals; dried fruits (especially dried apricots and figs); nuts (except peanuts). Zinc is essential for improving skin condition and stimulating the activity of hair follicles. This element is found in pumpkin seeds, some vegetables, cereals and seafood. But you need to be careful. Seafood can cause allergies, and seeds and nuts are high-calorie foods, so they can only be consumed in small quantities. Multivitamin complexes are taken strictly in the dosage indicated by the doctor, because an excess of such substances can be no less dangerous than a deficiency.

CONCLUSIONS

If, according to the results of the studies, deviations are found that may indicate serious metabolic disorders, blood pathology, internal organs, the doctor will refer for consultation to other specialists, for example, an endocrinologist, hematologist, etc.

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